

DEDICATION OF ACTIVITIES OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM TO THE CREATION OF ALISHER NAVAIY

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Abstract: This article provides recommendations on the analysis of Mir Alisher Navoi's work in the activities of extracurricular clubs in the general secondary school.

Key words: Extracurricular activity, methodology, Alisher Navoi, ghazal, epic, scientific activity.

The book is considered an engineer of the conscious life and spiritual world of mankind. A book is an infinite world: the bosom is wide, the sky is high, the bottom is deep. According to the sages, the book is a source of knowledge, a treasure of wisdom collected by humanity, a product of social consciousness. As the great poet and thinker Navoi Baba wrote: "The book is a great teacher, the main source of knowledge and spiritual growth." In the language of our people, there are many proverbs about the importance of reading books and getting proper education, studying science, and learning a profession. For example, "A mind without a book is a bird without wings", "A sign of happiness is knowledge", "Knowledge is a lamp of the mind", "Beauty is in knowledge and enlightenment", "Knowledge brings happiness, knowledge brings a throne", "Craft is a flowing spring, knowledge is a burning lamp", "Get gold, get knowledge, if you get knowledge, learn". Such auspicious stories can be continued for a long time.

It is not an exaggeration to say that today, in a period of rapid development of our country, the attention to the formation of book reading and reading culture, reflected in the minds of the wise, has risen to the level of state policy. Realizing the incomparable role of book reading in the comprehensive formation of the young generation, on January 12, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting the culture of book reading and reading" "On the creation of a commission" was adopted. In this order, it is necessary to attract a wide segment of the population to reading books, to widely promote reading and reading, to raise our children to be fond of books from the kindergarten age, to pay attention to the content of book products, and to improve the quality of their printing. and ensuring that it reaches remote villages and farms, increasing the number of bookstores filled with books of

various contents, paying special attention to enriching the library fund, promoting the published books among the population on the basis of mass media - it is planned to pay special attention to the organization of advertisements, raising interest and conducting various contests among active librarians and promoters in this process. Of course, reading classes in elementary grades have a great contribution in carrying out work in this direction. The study of works of art is important in the development of students' worldview and speech richness in the primary grade.

It is known to all of us that it is the most valuable thing to spread the call to reading in the image of our great genius Alisher Navoi. With this in mind, we would like to recommend the following methods of conducting, teaching and promoting work on the activities of Hazrat to elementary school students based on the extracurricular activities that we have practiced in our personal experience:

1. Oral promotion of Alisher Navoi's works (oral promotion): Interviews. Conversations can be in classes, groups and individually. In this case, it is recommended to read a work or teaching of Alisher Navoi. Then classes, parallel classes, groups, and one-on-one conversations are held, periodically or in a fixed order, as a result of which a doctrine is studied, elaborated, and cooked. For example: If you don't care about a person, you are a demagil person, and the people who don't have me are sad.

2. Promotion of Alisher Navoi's works on the basis of an exhibition can be recommended as follows:

- 1) organizing a sample exhibition of Alisher Navoi's works - books;
- 2) "Alisher Navoi - a generous person", "Alisher Navoi - a great poet", "Alisher Navoi and Independence", "Publication of Alisher Navoi's works during the years of independence", "Books you read", "Teachings of Alisher Navoi" , preparing posters and stands dedicated to the works of Alisher Navoi, "Epics written by Alisher Navoi", "Examples of Alisher Navoi's pamphlets", issuing wall newspapers dedicated to Alisher Navoi's works and historical dates;
- 3) memorizing the instructive thoughts and quotes from the works of Alisher Navoi;
- 4) making a list of Alisher Navoi's works that students should read;
- 5) writing essays on Alisher Navoi's life, activities, works, organizing an exhibition of samples of written essays;

6) Samples of students' drawings of Alisher Navoi's work and works. The exhibition of paintings called "Our Grandchildren of Alisher Navoi" consists of 7 sections and can be named as follows:

1. *"Childhood of Alisher Navoi"*.
2. *"Alisher Navoi, a philanthropic person"*
3. *"My decorations to the works of Alisher Navoi"*.
4. *"The heroes of Alisher Navoi's works are in my work."*
5. *"Alisher Navoi and the children of Uzbekistan"*.
6. Like *"I am the grandson of Alisher Navoi."*
7. *"Our gift to our grandfather Alisher Navoi"*.

It is advisable to use materials from newspapers and magazines to further enrich the above exhibitions.

3. Conducting audio readings of Alisher Navoi's works. Excerpts from the works of Alisher Navoi, audio recordings of the master of words, poems will be read to the students through simple or technical means, or an expressive reading competition will be held.

4. Conducting roundtable discussions on the works of Alisher Navoi. For example: "Alisher Navoi and children", "Happy childhood", "Alisher Navoi - the poet I love", "Uzbekistan - my homeland".

5. Holding question-and-answer evenings on the works of Alisher Navoi. It will be the same if the people of grain, veterans and industrial pioneers, teachers take part in these events.

6. Conducting discussion evenings on the works of Alisher Navoi.

7. Organization of oral newspapers and magazines based on the works of Alisher Navoi. Readers' opinions, views and attitudes about Alisher Navoi's poems, epics and wisdom will be heard.

Using the above suggestions and recommendations as much as possible depends on the professional skills of the teacher, and there is no doubt that these opinions can serve to a certain extent for the spiritual development of each student.

References:

1. Alisher Navoi. Layli and Majnun (with Nayoni Nasri). - Tashkent: G. Ghulom publishing house, 2006.
2. Tahirov.S "Hibbatul-haqaiq" epic of Adib Ahmad Yugnaki: text research and analysis. Samarkand. SamDU edition 2009.

